

THE INCORPORATION OF TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The integration of technology into education has created a new way of teaching and learning. Technology integration in teaching English is significant as it enhances students' engagement and creativity as well as interactivity with peers. Technology plays an essential role in making learning dynamic and motivating. Utilizing online language learning applications, online teaching and learning resources, and computer-based language games is beneficial for students in their language learning and acquisition process. This paper reviews the relevant literature on the incorporation of technological tools and platforms in teaching the English language. Research showed that the integration of technology into English classrooms equips students with the necessary digital literacy skills for effective communication skills, collaboration, creativity, and innovation. Embracing technology in English language education makes learning more entertaining, engaging, and accessible both for teachers and students. Therefore, adopting technological tools to create a more dynamic learning environment is crucial.

Keywords: technology, teaching, English language, dynamic learning environment, innovation

INTRODUCTION

There are various definitions of technology by researchers. According to Isman (2012), technology is a means of carrying out a task, specifically using technology processes, techniques, or expertise. It is also the utilization of knowledge in practice, especially in a particular field. Utilizing technology involves organized engagements with individuals, machinery, and the surroundings, encompassing various tools and platforms. As per Abdelaty and Saleh (2023), the incorporation of technological tools and resources to enhance the educational process in English language teaching is termed technology integration. This integration can manifest in diverse ways, such as incorporating multimedia resources, utilizing online learning platforms, and integrating digital games, among other methods.

Teachers incorporate various creative teaching strategies and methods using technology in teaching English. These include playing games like Hangman and Simon Says, storytelling, using music and songs, using educational apps, and classic role-playing and group discussions (Taula'bi', 2022). It could also be specific to a particular subject, like the creative teaching strategy called Hot Seating, which involves students interviewing characters from the story they have read (Andrews et al., 2021). These are just some of the innovative approaches in the

teaching-learning process. These methods and strategies can be incorporated with educational theories that have proven to be timelessly effective in addressing students' needs.

According to Mofareh (2019), incorporating cutting-edge technology into English language instruction has become imperative, particularly considering the remarkable progress in various fields. To stay abreast of the worldwide technological revolution, the education sector needs to embrace modern tools such as computers, multimedia devices, mobile phones, audio/visual applications, and social media. This will optimize English language instruction and give teachers the tools they need to connect with their students in a sophisticated and methodical way. Susikaran (2013) pointed out that classrooms and teaching approaches have undergone significant modifications due to the inadequacy of the traditional chalk-and-talk method in effectively instructing the English language. According to Raihan and Han (2012), with the integration of technology into education, students learn effectively in a well-organized and interactive classroom environment. In this way, lessons delivered via lectures traditionally are less successful and effective than lessons delivered using technology. In the Philippine context, Elsit (2023) investigated the effects of artificial intelligence (AI) integration on the effectiveness of language training, as well as the advantages and difficulties that students perceive, variations in learning results, and the possibility that it could close the digital divide. According to research, artificial intelligence (AI) improves learning effectiveness, provides individualized training, and fills in gaps in distant learning environments. Nonetheless, difficulties and the significance of pedagogical balance became apparent. The study emphasizes that in order to fully realize AI's potential, adaptive instructional approaches are required. Limitations and future directions are highlighted, highlighting the significance of the study for influencing ELT's future. Although English language teachers may have not studied technology and may not be computer experts, they should discover ways to use technology as a valuable learning tool for their students in order to enhance the learning process.

TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH

This section involves reviewing relevant studies on the integration of technology in teaching the English language. The researchers employed a systematic approach to identify related literature for this study. The inclusion criteria are centered on studies published in recent years, focusing on utilizing technological tools to facilitate English language teaching in order to ensure a comprehensive and representative selection of literature to support the research objectives.

Innovative teaching has been transformed by using technology as a motivational strategy, offering a wealth of opportunities for both teachers and students. By integrating technology into English language instructional approaches, teachers can craft dynamic and interactive learning experiences that capture students' imagination and curiosity. Technology tools, such as virtual reality simulations and gamified learning platforms, provide a diverse range of resources for creating captivating and immersive lessons that deeply resonate with students. These technology-based strategies and methods, which incorporate interactive elements, multimedia presentations, and real-world applications, foster active engagement and collaboration, empowering students to become active participants in their educational journey. As a motivational strategy, technology inspires a love for learning, nurtures creativity, and fosters critical thinking skills, ultimately equipping students to thrive in an ever-evolving, technology-driven world.

Technology usage as a motivating approach in the classroom has the potential to be highly significant and advantageous. The importance of technology in teaching English cannot be overstated since it has significantly enhanced the education landscape. In fact, technology has the capacity to engage and encourage students in a variety of ways, boosting their learning skills and experience as well as their overall academic success. Through the internet,

technology makes it simple to access enormous amounts of information. This makes it possible for both students and teachers to learn about various subjects and keep up with the most recent advancements across numerous disciplines. Many researchers (Colreavy-Donnelly et al., 2022; Bizami et al., 2023; Panagiotidis et al., 2023) believe that teachers should integrate technological platforms or tools into the English classroom because it has the potential to positively impact both students and teachers.

Incorporating technology as an innovation accelerator into the English language classroom enhances student engagement and interactivity during the learning process. Educational applications, multimedia presentations, and gamified learning platforms are some of the tools that can captivate students' interest and nurture their curiosity. According to Ampa (2021), technological competence is positively related to innovative teaching performance. Teachers should utilize their competencies in implementing innovative teaching approaches and methods in the classroom to enhance the learning process. Therefore, it can be said that technology is unquestionably facilitating the development of creative teaching strategies. The incorporation of technology in English classes has unlocked fresh prospects and avenues for educators to rethink and elevate their instructional techniques and teaching strategies. Although technology is beneficial, it should not diminish the significance of effective teaching methods and strategies and the teacher's role in guiding and supporting students' learning. Depending solely on technology for information may result in superficial learning, potentially hindering the development of critical thinking and analytical skills among students.

Over the last couple of decades, AI has brought about the emergence of multiple tools with the potential to transform academic programs. In the context of the ongoing investigation, particular attention is given to tools designed to enhance academic writing (Mohammed et al. 2023). As an example, Grammarly, which operates as a digital writing aid service, is an online platform specializing in proofreading that is capable of scrutinizing documents for grammatical errors, originality, style, and editorial improvements (Al-Kadi, 2023; Karyuatry, 2018). Additionally, it offers word suggestions aimed at assisting students in refining their writing abilities. Noteworthy findings from Nazari et al. (2021) indicate that Grammarly played a role in nurturing students' self-regulation skills, attributing this to its diverse accessibility options, user-friendly interface, and the chance to rectify errors before final evaluations.

According to Rincon-Flores et al. (2022), gamification is commonly perceived as an instructional approach that prioritizes student involvement and motivation. Typically, it consists of dynamics, mechanics, and elements. They stated that gamification, through the mechanics of rewards, can be a tool that allows for improving virtual educational environments.

Kukulka -Hulme et al. (2022) studied new forms of teaching, learning, and assessment to guide educators and policymakers. They stated that flipped classrooms and blended learning inside and outside the classroom enhance innovative teaching strategies. They added that by embracing the concept of a 'flipped classroom' approach to more effectively blend distinct avenues of in-person and online synchronization, facilitating collaboration, discourse, and evaluation, educators can apply a flexible hybrid approach. Moreover, employing asynchronous activities for individual and collective tasks to establish foundational understanding and foster a sense of unity among learners contributes to innovative teaching strategies.

As stated by Cowie and Sakui (2021), teacher videos have gained significant popularity as a valuable tool for online learning. These videos not only facilitate digital literacy and academic integrity but also aim to enhance the effectiveness of current teaching strategies. In essence, the use of technology allows for a complementary approach to existing teaching techniques and strategies. This represents an authentic pedagogical advancement, enabling videos to revolutionize and redefine the landscape of language instruction. Therefore, incorporating teacher videos into online learning exemplifies how creative and innovative teaching

strategies have embraced technology to improve language instruction. These videos serve as a valuable educational resource that complements conventional teaching methods, enabling educators to craft more captivating, efficient, and personalized learning opportunities for students.

Astutik et al. (2022) believe that technology can be used to supplement an existing teaching technique to improve creativity and innovation in teaching the English language. This represents a sincere pedagogical progression, where videos can be employed to revolutionize and reshape how language instruction is conducted. The pedagogical progression envisioned by Astutik et al. (2022) embraces the concept of technology as a constantly evolving tool. With ongoing technological advancements, fresh opportunities to enhance English language instruction will arise. This flexibility ensures that educators remain at the forefront of pedagogical innovation, continuously striving to enhance teaching efficacy and student achievements. In addition, their perspective highlights the positive impact of technology when thoughtfully integrated into the teaching landscape. By embracing this approach, educators can create an enriched and inclusive learning environment where creativity and innovation flourish and students are equipped with the skills necessary for success in the rapidly evolving digital age.

Suwartono et al. (2022) stated that the term "innovation" is commonly linked to technology, particularly when it comes to education. In the context of education, innovation is frequently described as a technological transformation in teaching and learning methods. However, innovative education goes beyond technology; it encompasses the expertise in designing instructional activities that engage students, stimulate their motivation to learn, and enhance critical and innovative thinking skills, all within a positive and conducive learning environment. The relationship between innovation and teaching is interdependent, as innovative teaching serves as a crucial cornerstone for nurturing creative learners. The study by Suwartono et al. (2022) presents a compelling and positive argument regarding the association of the term "innovation" with technology, particularly in the realm of education. Their perspectives highlight the significance of technology as a means to facilitate innovative English teaching methods. However, the researchers emphasize that innovation in education transcends mere technological advancements.

Bizami et al. (2023) carried out research exploring the effectiveness of progressive pedagogical concepts and technological tools in immersive blended learning. They examined the alignment of three Education 4.0 innovative pedagogies—namely, heutagogy, peeragogy, and cybergogy—with the functionalities of three technological learning tools: Facebook, Learning Management System (LMS), and Blog. The findings of their research revealed that the cognitive factor is most strongly associated with the four primary functionalities of technological learning tools, namely time, self-directed learning, learning tasks, and community-related learning. This mapping aids teachers in devising teaching strategies by selecting appropriate technological learning tools that align with Education 4.0 pedagogies. It facilitates the optimization of immersive, blended learning practices.

ChatGPT as a technological tool can be beneficial when it comes to innovative English language teaching strategies. Hong (2023) argues that given the inevitability of ChatGPT, teachers and educational institutions should view it as a chance to innovate the traditional, century-old approaches to teaching and evaluation. The assertion is made that ChatGPT presents significant chances for educators and educational institutions to enhance second/foreign language teaching and assessments through innovative teaching approaches. Moreover, it has opened up various research avenues for researchers, particularly in the pursuit of a more personalized learning experience. Kim et al. (2023) explored the utilization of ChatGPT as a second language learning tool and scrutinized its suitability. The findings of their study revealed that to use ChatGPT effectively and ethically in education, it is

essential to create novel task types that necessitate human-like creative and critical thinking skills. This measure is crucial to mitigate the risks of potential misuse. It can be argued that the incorporation of ChatGPT in teaching English can foster dynamic and student-centered learning environments. It can serve as a creative writing aid, inspiring learners to delve into their imaginations and refine their creative writing abilities. Furthermore, ChatGPT's real-time question-answering and explanation capabilities can encourage critical thinking and problem-solving skills which play an important role in an innovative and creative learning-teaching environment. Regarding assessment, ChatGPT introduces innovative evaluation approaches and methods that can be beneficial for teachers. Its ability to analyze written responses allows for more intricate and thorough assessments of students' comprehension and skill levels. In addition, it facilitates continuous monitoring of student progress, empowering educators to pinpoint areas for improvement and customize their innovative teaching strategies accordingly.

The studies mentioned above talk about the advantages of technology integration in teaching the English language. In different contexts (various countries, cultures, student backgrounds, etc.), it can be deduced that teachers can benefit from the use of technology especially in modern times, where technology is inevitable. In other words, the above studies offer valuable opportunities for enhancing student engagement, learning experiences, creativity, critical thinking, and English language skills. Therefore, technology serves as a powerful motivational strategy and presents exciting prospects for effective English language teaching. The researchers suggest the following for future directions: the integration of virtual and augmented reality, a focus on ethical and inclusive tech practices, and the continuous creation of cutting-edge language evaluation instruments.

It can be concluded that technology has a crucial role in bolstering creative and innovative teaching strategies. It has become a potent catalyst, transforming the field of education through its support for inventive and imaginative teaching strategies and methods. By harnessing technology, educators can break free from traditional teaching techniques and adopt innovative approaches and strategies that ignite curiosity, encourage creativity, and foster critical thinking in students. As technology continues to progress, it holds the potential for even more significant advancements in education, empowering both teachers and students to realize their fullest potential and shape a brighter future for generations to come. Embracing technology in education is not merely an investment in the future; it also stands as a testament to the profound impact of technology on the art of teaching and learning when it comes to English classes.

CONCLUSION

This study is significant because it reviews the literature and highlights the benefits of technology, including enhanced student engagement, creativity, and critical thinking skills. Moreover, this review discussed the integration of various technologies such as gamified platforms, ChatGPT, and virtual reality simulations which contribute to innovative and creative English language teaching. In summary, the integration of technology into teaching English has enhanced the learning process. Teachers should adopt technological tools to create a more dynamic learning environment where students can enjoy the interactive learning environment to improve their critical thinking skills and innovation. English language teachers should use various teaching strategies and methods, such as online platforms, multimedia resources, as well as digital games to foster students' problem-solving skills and creativity. This technology-driven strategy makes learning more interesting and successful. Therefore, educators should embrace the power of technology when it comes to teaching the English language to inspire students to become more active in the process of learning and acquisition. The integration of technology into English language teaching offers a great opportunity for both teachers and students to thrive in a technologically interlinked world. Finally, teachers

should keep in mind that technology is not merely a tool, but it functions as a catalyst for fostering creativity, innovation, motivation, and excellence in teaching the English language in the classroom.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR (*optional*)

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